

VOICI - Solutions for voice interaction towards natural crew assistant

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Topic Manager: Thales

The main goal is to provide a proof-of-concept demonstrator at TRL 3, that is capable of listening to the communications occurring in an aircraft cockpit, recognizing and interpreting speech content, interacting with the crew and fulfilling crew requests, so as to simplify crew tasks and reduce workload.

Main objective: to develop/demonstrate an intelligent natural crew assistant in a cockpit environment up to TRL 3.

Obj. 1: Develop a non-intrusive voice acquisition system that allows separating speakers from each other and filtering speakers from background noise. The ambition is to acquire speech input of sufficient quality from both (i) crew headsets and (ii) an ambient microphone array system.

Obj. 2: Develop an audio evaluation environment emulating the audio environment in the cockpit.

Obj. 3: Develop a high-end speech recognizer that reaches a word error rate (WER) of 5% in this challenging cockpit environment. This engine will recognize not only aircrew requests but also inputs from the ATC radio communication.

Obj. 4: Develop an intelligent agent that naturally interacts with the aircrew and the existing aircraft system through pre-defined flight scenarios and that is aware of the flight situation through communication with other cockpit sub-systems and flight procedures.

Obj. 5: Develop the whole system in such way that it can be ultimately embedded in the cockpit without external dependencies with external cloud-based services.

Obj. 6: Test and evaluate the performances of the system under several flight phases with the defined high-level requirements.

Work Packages:

VOICI

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